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Gender Discrimination in Nigerian Schools: Implications for Decision Making for School Administrators

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***Abstract:** The paper explores the various factors contributing to gender discrimination in schools in Nigeria. Gender discrimination and gender imbalance are obstacles to women and girls' development because it has the potential to create a gap in admission into educational institutions, employment opportunities, appointment into leadership positions, empowerment and development that is based on sex. The paper is a review paper. Secondary data were used in the paper. The secondary data were collected from online publications and print materials. Content analysis was adopted to select the final literature used in the paper. The paper identified culture and traditions, early marriage practices, political factors, poor implementation of various gender policies, religious factors, and economic status as factors responsible for gender imbalance in schools in Nigeria. The study recommends among other things that; governments at all levels should partner with religious and traditional institutions to roll out an advocacy initiative that will advocate for equal opportunity for male and female genders in having access to education in addition to discouraging early marriage that discourages female gender from pursuing education. The suggested solution will increase the level of manpower development among the female gender in political consideration and other leadership positions.*

***Key words:** Gender Imbalance, academia, gender sensitivity.*

1.0 Introduction

Gender inequality saturates all aspects of Nigerian life. They manifest in the family institutions, educational sector, labour market, politics and social service institutions. Indeed, discrimination against women in Nigeria is manifested within and outside the home (UNESCO, 2016). Gender discrimination is a phenomenon that has negative implications for the development of organizations and people. Gender discrimination is obstacles against the employment or appointment into leadership

positions or authority of an individual based on sex. It is a deprivation of the rights of the individual that could have contributed positively to the development of the organization and society at large. These rights include political, marriage/family and employment (Okon, 2016).

Gender discrimination refers to the practice of granting or denying rights or privileges to a person based on their gender. This kind of discrimination leads to unfair treatment directed at an individual or a group based on their gender which denies them their rights, opportunities or resources (Chauraya & Mugodzwa, 2012 in Olaogun, Adebayo, & Oluyemo 2015). Gender discrimination is closely related to gender stereotypes and sexism which often is a barrier to developing a harmonious working environment. This kind of discrimination manifests in the form of sexist language, sexual harassment or discrimination on the job (Maruzani, 2013 in Olaogun, et al 2015). Gender discrimination is a war against peace-building in society, and Nigerian schools in particular. Therefore, it has been argued that reduction in gender discrimination entails that the female gender has equal ability with their male counterpart (Ayeni, Ogunode, & Nonyelum, 2024).

Gender discrimination is in every society but problematization is common in Africa with its patriarchal system having absolutely dangerous implications manifesting in educational institutions. While several efforts have been underway to rectify gender discrimination, much remains to be done across all educational sectors. There seems to be a natural gender role distinction all over the world, which has created a gap in opportunities between men and women (Nwajiuba, 2011).

1.1 Purpose of the study

The objective of the study is to explore and analyze the factors responsible for gender discrimination in Nigerian schools.

1. Theoretical Framework

This study employed role theory. This theory was postulated by Robert Merton in 1957. Role theory is the theory that explains the fact that people's behaviour is the performance of roles that society expects from them. These people strive to meet these roles, which comprise certain expectations, and behaviours. Ideally, the political elite is supposed to ensure that there is sustainable peace in society by ensuring that there is no discrimination and marginalization of persons based on gender. For instance, it has been noted that the inability of the governance system or structure to perform will cause the system to malfunction (Ayeni & Nwaorgu, 2018). The discrimination in society stems from the failure of the political elite to sufficiently perform their role of ensuring equality and fairness between male and female genders in society. Many female gender are not empowered because of their limited access to education that is expected to empower people to enable them to provide for their basic needs (Ayeni, Sani, Idris, & Uzoigwe, 2019). The challenge facing peace-building in Nigeria is weak institutions. People perform gender roles daily, meaning that their behaviours are shaped by societal expectations for them depending on their gender (S.M, 2022).

The implication of this theory to this paper is that the political elite have roles to play in ensuring that there is no discrimination of persons. These political elite are expected to carry out their functions and responsibilities in ensuring fair treatment irrespective of gender differences.

2. Method

This paper is a review paper and it explores the various factors contributing to gender discrimination in schools in Nigeria. The study employed a documentary research method or what is referred to as neo-positivism. The reason for using this method is that non-positivism is a system of enquiry for carrying out research that tries to explain social phenomena with the aid of a research question, without

necessarily testing hypotheses (Ayeni, Saman, & Sani, 2019). The study relies on published secondary data from reputable sources including a review of published articles from reputable international journals such as CEON, Elsevier, Hindawi, JSTOR, IEEE, LearnTechlib SAGE, Nebraska and Springer amongst others. This research work used the Content Analysis and elimination method in the selection and analysis of papers, journals and abstracts used for the article. The design adopted for this article was to show an understanding of gender discrimination in schools in Nigeria. This study employed the content analysis method by selecting the relevant content of the various literature related to this study; and the literature review enabled the overall development of the study, which ordinarily centred on theoretical and conceptual exploration (Adapted from Ogunode & Ajap, 2021 in Ayeni, Ogunode, & Nonyelum, 2024).

4.0 Data Analysis on factors responsible for gender imbalance in schools in Nigeria

Culture and traditions in Nigerian societies and communities are responsible for gender imbalance in the educational institutions in Nigeria. According to Enyioko (2017), various cultural and social values have historically contributed to gender disparity in education. Also, Nwajiuba, (2011), observed that one prominent cultural view is that the woman should stay home and learn to tend to her family instead of attending school. Okon (2016) noted a host of constraints with 'Nigerian tradition' being named at the top of the list. The 'Nigerian tradition' was explained as a tradition that attaches a higher value to a man than a woman, whose place is believed to be the kitchen. A study by the University of Ibadan linked the imbalance in boys' and girls' participation in schooling to the long-held belief in male superiority and female subordination. This situation was further aggravated by patriarchal practices which gave girls no traditional rights to succession. Therefore, the same patriarchal practices encouraged preference to be given to the education of a boy rather than a girl (NBS, 2018 cited in Enyioko 2017). Also, Nigerian society (both historical and contemporary) has been dotted with peculiar cultural practices that are potently hurtful to women's emancipation, such as early/forced marriage, wife-inheritance and widowhood practices. As daughters self-identify as females with their mother and sisters, and sons as males with their father and brothers, gender stereotyping becomes institutionalized within the family unit. Also, the dominant narratives of religion in both colonial and post-colonial Nigerian society privilege men to the detriment of women, even in educational accessibility (World Bank Group, 2015; Enyioko, 2017). According to Lauer and Lauer (2002), the traditional roles assigned to women inhibit their commitment to higher education, which in turn diminishes their prospects of formal labour participation. Females are withdrawn from school into marriages. While the male counterparts continue to pursue further education, the females are put under pressure to marry early because they are thought to require minimal education to become good wives.

The early marriage practices in Nigeria have led to few girls getting admission into tertiary institutions and this has also led to a manpower development of female folks. This problem has according to Oluyemi, (n.d); Okeke (1997); Dada, Ogunode, & Ajayi, (2022); Ogunode Ahmed, and Yahaya (2021) reduced the number of women employed in educational institutions across the country. Early marriage has limited many women's opportunities in the labour market. Empirical evidence shows gender disparity in enrolment, retention and completion at all levels- primary, secondary, and tertiary. For example, ActionAid, (2011) discovered that in 15 northern states of Nigeria, the disparity in favour of boys is quite high. Among girls surveyed in six Northern States in 2008, 43% cited early marriage as a major obstacle that would prevent them from continuing their schooling and 32% cited pregnancy. Also, in the South-East, NPC, (2009) noted that where boys drop out and engage in income-generating activities to supplement household income the disparity is in the favour of girls. In 2008, 28% of young women aged 15-19 years surveyed for the DHS were currently married, compared to 1% of

young men. Among these young women, 12% were married by 15 years of age and 26% were already in a polygamous union with one or more co-wives. Early marriage practice in Nigeria has served as a barrier to gender equality in Nigerian schools. This is even as it has been noted that the inability of any structure to perform its function will cause the system to malfunction (Ayeni & Nwaorgu, 2018; Joseph, Cinjel & Ayeni, 2017). It seems that the structure that allows for early marriage without adequate training is a result of a structure that is not performing its function adequately. The above observation has been attributed to the failure of leadership in Nigeria (Ayeni, 2018).

Another factor contributing to gender imbalance in the schools in Nigeria is the political factor, especially in the tertiary institutions and in the selection of academic leaders. Olaogun, Adebayo, and Oluyemo (2015) opined that political factors are also strongly implicated. In Nigeria, there is no political will to implement International agreements that protect women's rights. Since females are not adequately represented in Nigerian politics, gender-sensitive laws and policies are not a priority either at the state or national level (Oladeji, 2009). As a result, there has been no attempt in the direction of looking into the minimum percentage of lecturers reserved for women in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria (Olaogun, et al 2015). However, scholars have faulted the low level of access to education as the reason for the absence of popular participation and involvement in the decision-making of government (Ayeni, 2017).

Poor implementation of various gender policies in Nigerian educational institutions especially the tertiary institutions has accounted for poor representation in every aspect of the educational institutions in Nigeria. To corroborate the above, it has been noted that the inability of the governance system or structure to perform its roles is also hurting the educational system (Ogunode, Ayeni, & Olorundare, 2024). Consequently, Edinoh, Odili, and Nwafor (2023) acknowledged poor implementation of gender policy on admission, recruitment and the selection of academic leaders has resulted in gender imbalance in most tertiary institutions. Specifically, Ogunode & Salman, (2022a) maintained that poor implementation of gender policy on recruitment is responsible for more males among the staff of the universities in Nigerian than the females and the poor implementation of gender policy on the appointment of universities manager and administrators gave males the upper hands in the occupation of leadership positions of the universities than the female folks (Ogunode et al 2022a). Ogunode & Ahmed (2021) noted that one of the important reasons why women have not received adequate benefits from years of planning and development is their inadequate representation which can be linked to the non-implementation of the gender acts and policies in Nigeria. Most gender policies designed and formulated to ensure gender equality in recruitment are poorly implemented in higher institutions. This is even though democracy itself is capable of bringing about political development where there is happiness for the greatest number of citizens (Ayeni & Sani, 2021). Consequent to the above, the Federal Ministry of Women Affairs and Social Development (2006); James (2014) and Deji (2016) concluded that the poor implementation of the Child Rights Act which was passed at the Federal level in 2003 has accounted for gender inequality in the schools. This has been attributed to the fact that the ruling elites employed laws and politics to rule Nigeria to their advantage to the detriment of the citizens (Godwin, Ayeni, Peter, 2021).

The various religions in Nigeria subscribe to the idea that the man is the head of the family and has greater control and decision-making powers. Almost all religions in Nigeria preach in favour of women's absolute domestic role. That is, women should be at home to care for their children and husbands without external engagements. The religious teachings hold that the woman is the weaker vessel and plays the second fiddle in a marriage partnership. As such, the woman is taught to be subservient to the man (Olaogun, et al 2015). The above development is not subservient to the notion

of conflict management which is supposed to be the methodologies employed to address violent conflict and ensure a peaceful atmosphere (Ogunode, Ayeni, & Samuila, 2024). Gender discrimination is not conflict management friendly.

The economic status of many Nigerian parents has resulted in gender imbalance in the schools in Nigeria. Many Nigerians cannot afford to sponsor their wards to tertiary institutions because of the high cost involved. UNICEF (2005), discovered that many children do not attend schools in Nigeria because their labour is needed to either help at home or to bring additional income into the family. Many parents cannot afford the costs of sending their children to school in addition to buying uniforms and textbooks for their wards. For others, the distance to the nearest school is also a major hindrance, cultural bias; most parents do not send their children to school, rather they prefer to send them to Qur'an school. Even when children get enrolled in school, they do not finish the primary cycle. The reason for this low completion rate includes child labour, economic hardship and early marriage for girls. Also, Lawal and Muhammed (2014) found out that the socio-economic status of parents, parental occupation and early marriage, and academic factors are the causes of the gender gap in science and technology education. Ogunode, Lawan and Yusuf (2021), opined that the economic status of many Nigerian parents has accounted for the gender imbalance in some Nigerian universities. With over 60% of Nigerians (almost 100 million people) living in poverty, on less than US\$1 per day, girls are often sent to work in markets or hawk wares on the street (Ogunode, et al 2022). The reason for the imbalance is that people who have no access to education cannot empower themselves since access to education is what empowers people to provide for their basic needs (Ayeni, Sani, Idris, & Uzoigwe, 2019). This has further led to a lack of financial security for the female gender. This is even as financial security is the capacity of people to provide for their survival (Ayeni, 2024). The ability of the female gender to provide for their basic need and those of their families has been hampered by a lack of access to education that results in the absence of financial security.

5.0 Findings of the Study

The study revealed the factors responsible for the gender imbalance in Nigerian schools include; Culture and traditions are responsibilities for the gender imbalance in educational institutions in Nigeria, early marriage practices in Nigeria have also led to manpower development of female folks, political consideration in the tertiary institutions' selection of academic leaders negatively affect female gender, there is poor implementation of various gender policies in Nigerian educational institutions, there is religions belief in Nigeria that man is the head of the family and also empower them with decision making powers that discriminate female gender, and lastly the socio-economic did not favour many female genders who are mostly full housewives in Nigerian,

6.0 Conclusion and Recommendations for Decision-Making in Schools

The paper explores the various factors contributing to gender discrimination in schools in Nigeria. The paper concluded that gender discrimination and gender imbalance practices are inimical to society and school development. It is a practice that has negative implications on the development of education and the societies at large. Gender discrimination and gender imbalance an obstacles to women and girls' development because it has the potential to create a gap in admission into educational institutions, employment opportunities, appointment into leadership positions, empowerment and development that is based on sex. The paper also, identified culture and traditions, early marriage practices, political factors, poor implementation of various gender policies, religious factors, and economic status as factors responsible for the gender imbalance in the schools in Nigeria.

Based on the findings of this study, the paper hereby recommends that: Governments at all levels should partner with religious and traditional institutions to roll out an advocacy initiative that will advocate for equal opportunity for male and female genders in having access to education in addition to discouraging early marriage that discourage female gender from pursuing education. The suggested solution will increase the level of manpower development among the female gender in political consideration and other leadership positions. Secondly, government at all levels should partner with traditional and religious leaders to advocate for the need for men to allow their wives to seek gainful jobs. The suggested solution will enhance the socio-economic well-being of the female gender.

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